

**GLOBAL WARMING AND THE FACTORS THAT CAUSE IT,
ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS RESULTING FROM IT**

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Annotation

Global warming is the long-term warming of the planet's overall temperature. Though this warming trend has been going on for a long time, its pace has significantly increased in the last hundred years due to the burning of fossil fuels. As the human population has increased, so has the volume of fossil fuels burned. Fossil fuels include coal, oil, and natural gas, and burning them causes what is known as the "greenhouse effect" in Earth's atmosphere.

Key words: global warming, CO₂, deforestation, chlorofluorocarbon, increasing temperature.

Global warming is the phenomenon of a gradual increase in the temperature near the earth's surface. This phenomenon has been observed over the past one or two centuries. This change has disturbed the climatic pattern of the earth. However, the concept of global warming is quite controversial but the scientists have provided relevant data in support of the fact that the temperature of the earth is rising constantly. There are several causes of global warming, which have a negative effect on humans, plants and animals. These causes may be natural or

might be the outcome of human activities. In order to curb the issues, it is very important to understand the negative impacts of global warming.

In addition, the climate is an inert and sensitive system. If, for example, a tipping point (e.g. the Gulf Stream or permafrost soils) in the climate system is reached or exceeded, this change is irreversible, i.e. it cannot be reversed. Other parts of the climate system (e.g. sea level) react sluggishly to changes in CO₂ concentration and show strongly time-delayed effects.

The current climate crisis differs from earlier climate changes mainly by its speed. Never before have so many greenhouse gases been emitted so quickly. The reason for the rising temperatures is that we humans emit too much greenhouse gas due to our way of life since industrialisation, thus increasing the greenhouse effect. More heat than normal is trapped in the earth's atmosphere and the average global temperature increases, or global warming takes place.

Deforestation

Plants are the main source of oxygen. They take in carbon dioxide and release oxygen thereby maintaining environmental balance. Forests are being depleted for many domestic and commercial purposes. This has led to an environmental imbalance, thereby giving rise to global warming.

Use of Vehicles

The use of vehicles, even for a very short distance results in various gaseous emissions. Vehicles burn fossil fuels which emit a large amount of carbon dioxide and other toxins into the atmosphere resulting in a temperature increase.

Chlorofluorocarbon

With the excessive use of air conditioners and refrigerators, humans have been adding CFCs into the environment which affects the atmospheric ozone layer. The ozone layer protects the earth surface from the harmful ultraviolet rays emitted by the sun. The CFCs have led to ozone layer depletion making way for the

ultraviolet rays, thereby increasing the temperature of the earth.

Industrial Development

With the advent of industrialization, the temperature of the earth has been increasing rapidly. The harmful emissions from the factories add to the increasing temperature of the earth.

In 2013, the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change reported that the increase in the global temperature between 1880 and 2012 has been 0.9 degrees Celsius. The increase is 1.1 degrees Celsius when compared to the pre-industrial mean temperature.

Agriculture

Various farming activities produce carbon dioxide and methane gas. These add to the greenhouse gases in the atmosphere and increase the temperature of the earth.

Overpopulation

An increase in population means more people breathing. This leads to an increase in the level of carbon dioxide, the primary gas causing global warming, in the atmosphere.

Volcanoes

Volcanoes are one of the largest natural contributors to global warming. The ash and smoke emitted during volcanic eruptions goes out into the atmosphere and affects the climate.

Water Vapour

Water vapour is a kind of greenhouse gas. Due to the increase in the earth's temperature, more water gets evaporated from the water bodies and stays in the atmosphere adding to global warming.

Melting Permafrost

Permafrost is frozen soil that has environmental gases trapped in it for several

years and is present below Earth's surface. It is present in glaciers. As the permafrost melts, it releases the gases back into the atmosphere, increasing Earth's temperature.

Forest Blazes

Forest blazes or forest fires emit a large amount of carbon-containing smoke. These gases are released into the atmosphere and increase the earth's temperature resulting in global warming.

Major effects of global warming:

Rise in Temperature

Global warming has led to an incredible increase in earth's temperature. Since 1880, the earth's temperature has increased by ~1 degrees. This has resulted in an increase in the melting of glaciers, which have led to an increase in the sea level. This could have devastating effects on coastal regions.

Threats to the Ecosystem

Global warming has affected the coral reefs that can lead to the loss of plant and animal lives. Increase in global temperatures has made the fragility of coral reefs even worse.

Climate Change

Global warming has led to a change in climatic conditions. There are droughts at some places and floods at some. This climatic imbalance is the result of global warming.

Spread of Diseases

Global warming leads to a change in the patterns of heat and humidity. This has led to the movement of mosquitoes that carry and spread diseases.

High Mortality Rates

Due to an increase in floods, tsunamis and other natural calamities, the average death toll usually increases. Also, such events can bring about the spread of diseases that can hamper human life.

All in all, the release of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere is the major cause of global warming. It can be reduced by setting a high price of carbon, increasing the biofuels production from organic waste, use of renewable energy like solar and wind power, safeguarding forests and improving energy efficiency and vehicle fuel economy.

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